

Boat-tail shape optimization studies for a payload fairing

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ABSTRACT

Flow over Rocket payload fairing is complex in transonic Mach number regime. It is essential to make detailed study in this Mach number regime for arriving at optimized design in terms of structural loads and geometric parameters of the payload fairing. In most of the bulbous heat-shield configurations, a boat-tail with certain angle from the fairing meets the stage next to it. Flow over the boat-tail may separate geometrically or it can be induced by shock at transonic Mach number. Large separated region may lead to higher unsteadiness, which is associated with the higher acoustic levels. In the present work, boat-tail shape optimization study has been carried out for an ogive payload fairing. Objective of this work is to find the boat-tail shape, which minimizes the total separation length in the boat-tail region while simultaneously minimizing the boat-tail length. Reduction in size of separated region may help in reduction in noise level in boat-tail as well as downstream region to it.

Key Words: Payload fairing, boat-tail, shape optimization

NOMENCLATURE

R_n = Nose Radius of ogive heat shield
 R_o = Ogive radius of the heat shield
 L_{cyl} = Length of the payload fairing (PLF) cylinder
 D = Diameter of the PLF cylinder
 d = Diameter of core
 L = Length of the boat-tail
 L_{sep} = Separation length of the separated region in boat-tail area
 θ = Boat-tail angle
 (x_1, y_1) & (x_2, y_2) = Coordinates of control points in Bezier curve
PLF= Payload fairing

1. INTRODUCTION

Extensive experimental as well as computational aerodynamic studies are required to arrive at optimal configurations for launch vehicle payload fairing [1]. The PLF of many launch vehicles

have a diameter larger than that of the core propulsion stages in order to accommodate larger satellites. This requires a boat-tail at the lower end of the PLF (Figure 1).

In the present work, the boat-tail shape has been optimized. Objective of this work is to find the optimum boat-tail shape, which can minimize the separated flow in the boat-tail region. As the extent of separated region behind the boat-tail can have impact on unsteady flows and acoustic levels in this region (i.e. cryo stage). First a boat-tail was parameterized using Bezier curve defined by four control points. CFD studies were carried out on a few hundred configurations in the design space at a representative transonic Mach number ($M=0.9$). Based on the objective function values, a simplified shape (stepped boat-tail) was selected. Further optimization study has been carried out with a stepped boat-tail configuration.

2. OPTIMIZATION STUDIES

First attempt of optimization was made by changing the shape of the boat-tail described by a Bezier curve. Here a total five independent variables were used to control the shape and length of the boat-tail. Bezier curve is having two intermediate control points that control the shape of the curve and it has two end points. This curve is chosen to study the wide variety of boat tail shapes. Figure-1 shows schematic diagram of a typical ogive heat-shield configuration.

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Boat-tail shape is replaced by the Bezier curve (presented in Figure 2).

Figure 1 Typical ogive heat shield configuration

Figure 2 Boat tail shape as Bezier curve with five independent variables

Here point at the cylinder boat-tail junction is kept fixed (results in fixed cylinder length) while other end can move in x direction. Hence, there are five independent design variables. To begin with, Mach number 0.9 is selected for the studies. Finally selected configuration is tested for different Mach numbers ($M=0.8$ and 0.95) as well.

Optimization problem is defined as follows -

Minimize separation length (L_{sep}) and boat-tail length (L) at $M=0.9$.

Design variable bounds for this problem are as follows -

$$10^\circ \leq \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{D-d}{2L} \right] \leq 50^\circ$$

$$0 \leq x_1 \leq L, \quad 0 \leq x_2 \leq L,$$

$$0.5 * (D - d) \leq y_1 \leq 0.5 * D,$$

$$0.5 * (D - d) \leq y_2 \leq 0.5 * D$$

Axisymmetric CFD simulations are carried out using CFD++ software. Pointwise software has been used for the grid generation. Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) is used for generating the random samples for the design points, which are used for varying the control points and length of the boat-tail. Total 100 samples are generated for exhaustive search in this study. Grid convergence for separation length is obtained by changing the grid points over the boat-tail. First cell height is kept small to ensure y^+ of the order 1. SST $K-\omega$ turbulence model is used for the simulations. Domain 100 times of PLF diameter (100 D) is used for all the simulations.

Figure 3 shows plot of total separation length (L_{sep} in meters) and the boat-tail to boat-tail length (L in meters) for all 100 configurations. Here each dot represents separation length corresponding to a boat-tail configuration.

Figure-3 Separation length vs. boat-tail length (for test samples)

Following observations are made from the analysis -

- For majority of the boat-tail shapes, separation extent lies between 5 to 6 units.
- For many cases, with increase in boat-tail length, Separation distance reduces (as expected).
- Few interesting configurations are observed, which have lower boat-tail length as well as lower separation length.

A surrogate model was created from this set of data. However, it was found that the number of data points (configurations) were not sufficient to capture the objective function variation with design variables. Hence, the above CFD simulations were analyzed to select candidate simplified configuration for further studies.

2.1 Selected configuration for further optimization studies

Based on the above observations, a configuration (showing smaller separation length as well as relatively small boat tail length) is selected for further studies at different Mach numbers. This particular configuration is shown in Figure 4. It has a fairly small boat-tail angle followed by a small blunt base. Based on this configuration, a stepped configuration is derived which is a straight boat-tail with step in the end.

Figure 4 Selected configuration for further optimization study

Figure 5 Corresponding stepped configuration and straight boat-tail of same length

Figure 5 presents stepped boat-tail configuration, derived from the selected configuration and corresponding straight boat-tail configuration (conventional boat-tail). All these configurations have same boat tail length.

Simulations are carried out over these configurations for $M=0.8, 0.9$ and 0.95 and separation lengths, Turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) levels downstream of it are compared.

Results from the simulations show that separation length is lower for Bezier and derived stepped configurations in comparison to the conventional straight boat-tail. Also TKE levels downstream of BT are also lower for these configurations in comparison to straight BT.

Table-1

Boat-tail shape	L_{sep}/h_{step} (M=0.8)	L_{sep}/h_{step} (M=0.9)	L_{sep}/h_{step} (M=0.95)
Straight	4.96	5.55	7.21
Bezier	1.50	1.72	4.42
step	2.27	2.27	3.97

Here $h_{step}=0.5*(D-d)$

Table-1 shows comparison of normalized separation length for different boat-tail shapes at different Mach number.

This study shows that separation length is high at Mach number 0.95 . Stepped configuration gives minimum separation length among the Bezier, stepped and conventional boat-tail configuration at this Mach number. Also it will be easier to design and manufacture the stepped configuration shape in comparison to Bezier shape. Hence further optimization work has been carried out on the stepped boat-tail shape configuration at $M=0.95$.

2.2 Optimization studies for the stepped configuration

Figure 6 Stepped boat tail configuration used for further optimization studies

Figure 6 shows stepped boat-tail configuration used for further optimization studies. For this study, variation in length is between L_{min} and L_{max} , where L_{min} and L_{max} are selected as corresponding to 45° and 15° straight boat-tail lengths.

Total 7 stations are used for this length (5 equal divisions for the selected length variation as shown in

$$\Delta L = \frac{L_{max} - L_{min}}{5}$$

Figure-10). Here $\frac{L_{max} - L_{min}}{5}$. Also A corresponding length to 20 degrees boat tail (existing vehicle configuration) is also simulated at $M=0.95$. The choice of this Mach number was based on the previous optimizations study, which shows higher separation length at this Mach number.

Figure 7 Separation length vs. boat-tail angle with variation in BT length (M=0.95)

Figure 7 shows graph for separation length versus boat-tail angle with variation in BT length for Mach number 0.95 . Here $L1$ to $L7$ are boat tail lengths in increasing order with constant increment of ΔL .

Following observations can be made from this –

With increase in boat-tail angle, separation distance reduces up to 7° as flow is attached over the stepped portion of the boat-tail. It separates (shock induced) for 8° onwards stepped boat-tail configuration. Also increase in boat-tail length results in lower separation length and same trends as above follows with variation in boat-tail angle for a given length.

2.3 Optimization Studies

With the above data set, for stepped boat-tail configurations, a model using RBF (Radial Basis Function) is constructed for the optimization studies. The optimization problem remains the same, i.e., minimization of the separation length and the minimization of boat-tail length. The RBF surrogate model predicts the separation length as a function of the boat-tail geometry parameters.

Figure 8 Separation length vs. boat-tail length with Pareto optimal front

Figure 8 shows separation length vs. variation of boat-tail length for all the simulated configurations along with the Pareto optimal front (black curve). Pareto optimal front represents the optimal solutions in the design space of a multi-objective problem. The optimization was carried out using Attractor Anchored Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm (A2- MOEA) [2], which is described in the next section.

Following observations can be made from Figure 7 and 8-

- For a given length, separation length reduces with increase in BT angle up to 7° . Then flow separates over BT at 8° angle (small separation bubble + separation after the step). Beyond 8° , separation length increase. Representative separation bubbles are shown in Figure 9 and 10.
- With increase in boat-tail length, above trend follows but separation length reduces for all angles (as seen in Figure 11 for the 7° stepped boat-tail configuration).

- Separation length is minimum for 7° BT angle with step corresponding to 15° boat-tail length.

2.4. Optimization Module

Attractor Anchored Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm (A2- MOEA) was employed to carry out multi-objective optimization. It employs Attractors in the objective space to maintain good spread and accelerate convergence of the Pareto Optimal Front [2].

2.5 Experiments with different turbulence models

SST k- ω model predicts separation due to adverse pressure gradient with reasonable accuracy but to be more confident, an exercise has been carried out over 7° & 8° stepped boat-tail configuration with various turbulence models to assess the separation bubble size in boat-tail region. SST k- ω , SA, cubic k- ϵ and realizable k- ϵ models are used for the numerical experiment. Table 2 gives normalized separation lengths for these two configurations with different turbulence models.

Table-2

Model	Separation length (L_{sep}/h_{step}) (7° step BT)	Separation length (L_{sep}/h_{step}) (8° step BT)
SA	3.74	4.12 *
SST	3.08	3.79 *
Cubic K- ϵ	2.96	2.72
Realizable K- ϵ	1.4189	1.2474

*Note- Separation length starting point is taken as starting of the small separation over BT

Following are the observations from this study-

- SA model give higher separation distance in comparison to SST while other two give slightly lower for 7° stepped boat-tail case.
- For 8° case, SA and SST show small separation bubble due to shock over the BT and a separated region is formed after the boat-tail. But cubic/realizable k- ϵ models show separated region only after the stepped boat-tail end.
- For 8° case with SST and SA single length is presented instead of breaking it into two separated zones as the bubble over the boat-tail just reattaches before the step.

Since SST and SA models show similar trends, SST model has been used for further CFD studies

Figure 9 Separation bubble after boat-tail region for 7° BT angle (Length corresponding to 15° conventional BT)

Figure 10 Separation bubble over and after boat-tail region for 8° BT angle (Length corresponding to 15° conventional BT)

Figure 9 and 10 show separated region (streamlines) for the 7° and 8° stepped boat-tail configuration with SST k- ω model. A small separation region over the boat-tail is seen for the 8 degree configuration.

2.6 Comparison with corresponding straight (conventional) boat tail

To assess the advantage of stepped boat-tail, these results are compared with the corresponding straight boat-tail configurations. Comparison is made for the Pareto optimal stepped boat-tail configuration results with the results of the conventional boat-tail configuration having the same boat-tail length. Following observations can be made:

- Smaller separated zone for the stepped boat-tail configuration in comparison to conventional boat-tail configuration (Figures 11 and 12).
- Lower peak turbulent kinetic energy levels (TKE) in the trailing region of boat-tail for stepped configuration in comparison to straight boat-tail (Figure 13). This may result in relatively lower acoustic levels in this zone.

Figure 11 Comparison of separation length for Pareto optimal front (optimized stepped boat tails) and conventional boat tails

Figure 12 Separated zone in boat tail region for conventional (15°) and stepped boat tail configuration (corresponding)

Figure 13 Peak TKE levels in boat tail region with increasing boat tail length (decreasing boat tail angle)

Results from the simulations shows that optimal stepped boat tail configuration have 16 % to 57 % lower separation length as compared to conventional boat tail.

Also, it is seen that optimal boat tail configuration have $\theta_{step-BT} \sim 7^\circ$.

One reason for the reduced separation distance is that the flow over the boat tail is attached and separates only downstream of it after encountering the step. As step height is small, separation length is also small.

It is also observed that the peak Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE) levels in the separated region are lower by 15% to 45 % as compared to conventional boat tail. It is seen that increase in TKE levels is associated with increase in OASPL levels [3], hence it is expected that OASPL levels will be relatively lower for optimum stepped boat tail configuration. Based on above studies, stepped boat-tail configuration is expected to perform better from the view point of unsteady levels downstream of the boat-tail. This needs to be verified through wind tunnel tests.

This configuration is further analyzed for Mach numbers 0.8, 0.85 and 0.9. Figure 14 shows variation for separation length with Mach number for stepped and corresponding straight boat-tail.

Figure 14 Variation in separation length with Mach number

Figure 14 shows variation in separation length with Mach number. It can be seen that the separated zone length downstream of the boat-tail region is lower for the stepped boat-tail in comparison to the conventional straight boat-tail shape at all simulated Mach numbers.

2.7 Effect of angle of attack

3D simulations are expensive to carrying out for a large number of configurations. Hence CFD simulations have been carried out only on one candidate configuration at 2° and 4° angles of attack for Mach number 0.95. Based on above optimization studies, the optimal stepped boat tail configuration having a length equal to that of a conventional boat-tail having 20° boat-tail was chosen for the study.

The CFD simulations show that the shock sitting over the boat-tail moves slightly forward in the windward region and slightly backward in the leeward region (Figure 15) at higher angles of attack. Flow does not separate anywhere over the stepped boat tail region at 2° angle of attack while at 4° angle of attack case, flow just lifts up at the edge close to the plane 90° to the strapon plane.

This suggests that boat-tail angle can be slightly less than 7° in consideration of 4° angle of attack case.

Figure 15 Mach palette for stepped boat-tail configuration ($M=0.95$, $\alpha=4^\circ$)

2.8 Effect of strapons

3D simulations are very time consuming and due to limited availability of resources at the time this work was being carried out, a reference [4] has been used to assess the possible effect of strapons for this configuration.

This work shows that effect of strapons is felt as slight rise in upstream pressure. Some differences were observed in total separation length due to presence of strapons. For Mach number less than 1, separated zone is slightly smaller for with strapon case ($M=0.95$) in comparison to core alone case. For $M=1.05$, large difference is observed due to upstream pressure rise in presence of strapon bow shock (large shock standoff distance). As Mach number increases, bow shock is closer to strapon and its upstream influence is minimal. This study [4] affirms that optimization studies can be carried out with core alone case and optimized configuration can be further assessed with strapons.

Figure 16 Recommended stepped boat-tail configuration

Further investigation to assess the advantages / limitations of stepped boat-tail configuration through the wind tunnel test are planned on a configuration with θ° ($\theta^\circ \leq 7^\circ$) stepped boat tail angle (Figure 16).

3. CONCLUSION

The boat-tail of an ogive payload fairing has been optimized to minimize the flow separation length downstream of the boat-tail and to minimize the length of the boat-tail. The study shows that a stepped boat tail configuration, with approximately 7° boat tail angle, results in significantly lower separation length as compared to a conventional boat-tail configuration of the same length. Also, it is seen that it results in lower Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE) levels downstream of the boat-tail as compared to the corresponding straight boat tail configuration. This is likely to result in lower aeroacoustic levels on the boat tail and the immediate downstream regions.

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REFERENCES

1. Aaditya N Chaphalkar, Archana Ravindran, Vinod Kumar, Pankaj Priyadarshi and V Ashok, "Multi-Objective Optimization of Ogive Payload Fairing for a Launch Vehicle," Proceedings of Symposium on Applied Aerodynamics and Design of Aerospace Vehicle (SAROD 2015), December 3-5, 2015, Thiruvananthapuram, India
2. Pankaj Priyadarshi, "Attractor Anchored Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm (A²-MOEA): Formulation Document and Results of Test Cases", Tech. Rep. IIST/MDO-Lab/01/2015, Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology, Trivandrum, 2015
3. VSSC internal report, "Qualitative assessment of OASPL levels with Turbulent Kinetic Energy over a launch vehicle", Amit Sachdeva, Archana Ravindran and Pankaj Priyadarshi.
4. VSSC internal report, "Transonic flow simulations over LVM3 truncated unsteady pressure model using Menter's SST turbulence model"